

A study on the effect of coffee scrap as a booster for yard waste composting

Lancy Lin

Basis International School Guangzhou

xi.lin13567-bigz@basischina.com

Abstract

Composting is a process in which nitrogen-rich and carbon-rich organic wastes undergo a series of decomposition to be recycled and used as a form of fertilizer for plants. Coffee ground is a kind of organic waste that contains a large amount of nitrogen that is capable of providing valuable resources that allow bacteria to conduct fermentation reactions and generate energy. In this study, I will be exploring the effect of coffee scraps as a form of catalyst that would help accelerate the rate of composting and also act as a booster to the nutritional value of the compost.

1. Introduction

1.1. What is composting

Composting is a process of decomposition in which nitrogen-rich and carbon-rich organic materials are mixed in a specific proportion so that the mixture can act as a beneficial fertilizer that can enrich soil and aid plant growth. Wastes such as food scraps and dry leaves can be recycled in this process. These wastes can be categorized into nitrogen-rich and carbon-rich materials, which both help maintain the well-being of the bacteria decomposers during the process while facilitating the mechanism of breaking down the organic materials.

Figure 1: How does composting work [1]

1.2. Kitchen and dish wastes and composting

Many households prefer to use composting as a method to deal with kitchen and dish wastes. Indeed, this method helps recycle some food waste and helps with responsible consumption of food resources. The United Nation's sustainable development goal number 12 primarily deals with consumption and production, and its sub-target 12.3 addresses food waste. According to the United Nations Environment Program, every year, 1 trillion dollars' worth of food is thrown away. Most of this wasted food is processed through landfill [2]. However, as more organic matter, such as kitchen wastes and dish wastes, goes through the process of landfill, the more methane gas it releases [3]. This would lead to global warming since methane is a greenhouse gas that traps more heat inside the atmosphere than carbon dioxide [us]. If more of this organic matter could be recycled and reused as fertilizers, then we can effectively reduce the amount of greenhouse gas emissions and also reduce the use of chemical fertilizers in agriculture and thus reduce soil degradation and water contamination. However, there are also limitations to this method of composting kitchen wastes and dish wastes since it produces a smelly odor and is also unsanitary. At the same time, if yard waste were used instead, the composting pile wouldn't produce any odor, and it would also be more sanitized. In this study, I will try to conduct a yard waste composting pile while using some kitchen waste to accelerate the process of composting.

1.3. The mechanism of different types of composting - the relationship of composting type and aerobic and anaerobic respiration

The main methods of composting could be sorted into two categories, aerobic and anaerobic. Bacteria in aerobic composting require the presence of oxygen to function and break down the organic materials,

Received: 23 November 2024 Accepted: 30 December 2024

Published: 25 January 2025

Citation: Lin, L. (2025). A study on the effect of coffee scrap as a booster for yard waste composting. *The Young Scientist*, 4(1), 136-141.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14740116>

while anaerobic composting, on the other hand, does not require the interaction between bacteria and air. The anaerobic method usually requires less organic material presence and less human effort to monitor the condition of the compost. However, the temperature of an anaerobic composting pile will never be high enough to kill the pathogens within the pile, and it would also require more time to obtain usable compost. The aerobic method requires more effort to control the moisture and the ratio of the carbon-rich and nitrogen-rich material. It also needs constant turning to ensure that the bacteria in all parts of the composting pile get access to oxygen. In some cases, the anaerobic method would be considered more suitable for household composting since it takes up less space and requires less effort. However, it would be smellier compared to the aerobic compost, which hardly produces any odor. In addition, the aerobic method would be more efficient as it could produce usable compost in a short duration of time.

1.4. Mechanism of Yard Waste Composting

Bacteria and fungus use oxygen to degrade plant fibers, mainly cellulose, that are hard to degrade by other organisms. During the process, bacteria and fungi obtain nutrients from the fermentation process; they turn the nutrients into energy, and a large amount of heat is generated, such that the temperature at the core of the composting pile can go up to above 60 degrees Celsius. The microorganisms grow into a large population, so both a carbon source and a nitrogen source are needed for them to function.

1.5. Testing coffee scrap as boosting in yard waste composting

Theoretically, since the presence of valuable nutrients such as nitrogen and carbon would facilitate the work of the beneficial bacteria, the addition of more intense nutrient sources such as tea leaves and coffee scraps would act as the perfect catalyst for composts. In this study, I will be testing the effect of coffee scraps on the decomposition of composting as well as its effect on plant health.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Compositing Materials Preparation

The method that was used for this experiment is called open-air composting, yard waste composting, or hot composting [4] in which heat is produced when microorganisms in the compost conduct fermentation processes in order to degrade the materials in the composting pile. In this experiment, the aim is to prove that the use of coffee grounds could accelerate the process of composting and that it could help reduce carbon emissions. The coffee grounds used in the experiment were collected from a Starbucks in Guangzhou. Green and brown materials, including dry grass and melon vine, were collected from the

Figure 2: Collected coffee scraps

Shenzhen University Longhua Biological Industry Innovation Research Institute Base (Fig. 3).

2.2. Compositing experiment

After the resources were collected, the green and brown materials were processed into pieces that were about 6 cm long using a trimmer. The two compost containers were built using wire mesh. The larger container has a diameter of 60 cm, and the smaller one has a diameter of 50 cm. The green and brown materials in both containers were mixed with a ratio of 1:1. However, in the smaller container, we filled the green material and brown material up to the 20 cm mark. In the second container, we measured the height of the materials to be 30 cm, and approximately 400 grams of coffee grounds that we collected from Starbucks were added in order to test our hypothesis. The coffee grounds and the compost have a 1:9 ratio. An equal amount of water was added to both piles to make sure that there was enough moisture for the microorganisms in the compost to work.

During the course of observation, temperature was measured twice a day for about 1 week. Then, when the temperature started to drop after the third time that the composting pile was re-mixed, we started to measure the temperature once every one or two days. Whenever the temperature

Figure 3: Collecting green material as the Longhua Bio-base

of the larger composting pile is observed to be higher than 40 degrees Celsius and the temperature of the smaller one higher than 34 degrees Celsius, I will re-mix both of the composting piles. This is to expose more of the materials that were previously at the bottom of the container to air so that the microorganisms in those materials would carry out fermentation. After 24-30 hours of composting, small white spots could be observed in the composting pile, indicating the activation of microorganisms in the composting pile. No additional species of microorganisms are required for the mechanism to work. All the microorganisms involved in the fermentation process originated from the green and brown materials collected from the bio-base.

2.3. Validation of compost

After 312 hr of composting, some portion of the soil was collected and sent back to Guangzhou for a validation experiment. In this experiment, radish was planted in three different types of soil: normal soil, coffee ground composts and normal soil with a 1:1 ratio, and ordinary compost plus normal soil at a 1:1 ratio. Three replicas are made for each

Figure 4: Measuring temperature of the composting pile

experimental group. This experiment is conducted to test the nutrient value of the composting soil and the amount of nutrient value that coffee grounds can accumulate in the soil. The normal soil serves as a control group to demonstrate the nutrients that a radish seed can receive without any compost. Radish was chosen for the experimental plant since it is a good indicator of soil health and nutrient availability. The period of this experiment was set to be 5 weeks since radish will harvest 3-5 weeks after it's planted. Pictures will be taken every 24 hours to record the growth of the radish over the course of 5 weeks. The point when the radish sprouts will also be recorded. When the experiment ends after 5 weeks, the stem length, stem width, and root length of the radishes will be compared to examine their health. The final health conditions of those radish sprouts would act as indicators of the nutrient value brought by composting soil and the coffee ground compost.

2.4. Measurement of germination experiment

After 5 weeks of germination, the radish sprouts were pulled out, and their health was examined through a series of scales. Some factors that are crucial in this examination are stem length, stem width, root length, and the number of leaves of the plant. These factors will be scaled based

Figure 5: Comparison of the two composting piles

on their importance in determining plant health and then added together in order to obtain a general measurement of plant health that could be used for comparison between the plants. We ranked the factors from most important to least important, which goes from stem length and number of leaves, then stem width, and after that we have root length, and at last leaf length.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Observation

When comparing the coffee compost and the ordinary compost, we can tell from Fig. 5b that the coffee compost has a deeper color. The coffee compost is also in smaller pieces in comparison to the ordinary compost. This indicates that the addition of coffee grounds does help accelerate the degrading process of compost.

3.2. Comparison between composting with and without coffee scraps: Temperature

During the composting process, the coffee ground compost was observed to have a higher temperature and a faster rate of degrading. Fig. 5c shows the temperature of the two composting piles at different points of the process. The slope of the graph indicates the rate of change in temperature over time. As shown in the graph, before the first time of turning, the temperature of the two piles initially rises at the same rate, but soon after the temperature of the or-

dinary composting pile starts decreasing. From the second time of turning to the third time, both piles have the same rate of change of temperature. However, after the third time of turning, the coffee ground compost shows a greater rate of obtaining and losing heat until the ordinary pile drops significantly from 168 hr to 288 hr. Regardless of the difference in change in temperature, the temperature of the coffee ground compost was higher than the ordinary compost throughout the composting process. Also, the resulting temperature of the coffee ground compost is 4 degrees Celsius higher than the ordinary compost with only green and brown material. But since the initial temperature of the coffee ground compost is also 4 degrees Celsius higher than the ordinary compost, we created Fig. 5d, which shows the change of temperature between each time period. We arrived at the conclusion that although the coffee ground compost has a more rapid rate of change of temperature at various points of the graph, it also has a faster rate of losing heat, thus resulting in the same amount of change of temperature of the two piles.

3.3. Comparison between composting with and without coffee scraps: Rate of decomposition

Nevertheless, the data did show that the coffee ground compost has a more rapid rate of degrading. Fig. 5e shows the height of the two composting piles at different points of the composting process. As we can see in Fig. 5e, the initial height of the coffee ground compost is 10 cm higher than the ordinary compost, and they decompose at approximately the same rate during the first 114 hr. After 114 hr, the rate of degrading of the ordinary compost gets slower and reaches a constant stage from 114 hr to 264 hr. According to Fig. 5f, the overall change in height of the coffee compost was larger than that of the ordinary compost. Over the course of 13 days, the coffee ground compost degraded over 47 percent, while the smaller pile degraded only 30 percent over time.

3.4. Comparison between the small composting pile to the larger composting pile

We also noticed that the maximum temperature that the large pile hit was 42 degrees Celsius and the maximum temperature that the small pile reached was 36 degrees Celsius. This didn't quite meet our expectation of hitting a peak of 60 degrees Celsius, probably due to the limited size of our piles. This limitation on the size of our composting pile would reduce the amount of bacteria in the pile as well as the pile's ability to store heat.

3.5. Temperature when the composting piles were remixed

I've also noticed an interesting phenomenon in which, whenever the composting piles were remixed to facilitate the fermentation of microorganisms, the temperature would

decrease significantly. This is because if the temperature got too high, the heat could kill off beneficial bacteria, and turning the pile would help release the excess heat and prevent these bacteria from dying. At the same time, turning the pile would allow the bacteria in the rest of the pile to aerate and continue breaking down the materials.

3.6. Result of the germination experiment

While I saw a decent result on building the composting piles, the result of the validation experiment wasn't very satisfying. After approximately 5 weeks of the germination period, the radish seed planted in both the coffee compost and the ordinary compost didn't sprout. However, the seeds in the normal soil that we got from my potted plants did sprout, proving that the seeds are qualified functioning seeds. There are two possible errors that might have led to this result. It is possible that not enough soil was mixed with the composts, thus providing a structure that is mostly hollow, which is insufficient for plant growth and root development. Another possibility might be that our compost is inadequate for facilitating plant growth. It might be that the height of my composting piles was too small for the green and brown material to degrade properly, or it is also possible that the diameter of my composting piles was too small for the piles to heat up to the temperature that favors the productivity of functional bacteria groups. Another factor that might lead to the failure of our compost might be the size of our green and brown material. We might have made the pieces so large that they didn't break down properly in a short period of time. The time taken to construct these composting piles is already shorter than the suggested time duration. Thus, making the materials too big might further delay the rate of composting, leading to a compost that isn't sufficient to act as fertilizer to aid plant growth.

3.7. The implication of this study

3.7.1 Experience summary on making composting pile

When constructing a compost, you might want to make sure that your material is chopped into the right size so that it can be broken down in a short period of time. When the composting piles were made, our green and brown materials were chopped into 4-6 cm pieces. Apparently, this is a bit too large for them to be broken down completely over the course of 2 weeks, which might be one of the major causes of the failure of my germination experiment. Fully broken down composts should have a dark brownish color while our compost has a light brown color. In addition, the size of the container is also critical throughout the process. According to the Maryland Department of the Environment, the ideal size of a compost would be at least 1 cubic yard, which is equivalent to approximately 0.76 cubic meters. My composting piles are slightly smaller than that, which is probably why our temperature is significantly

Figure 6: Validation Experiment Results

lower than the maximum of 160 degrees Fahrenheit, 71.11 degrees Celsius, suggested by the United States Environmental Protection Agency.

3.7.2 Suggestions for future works

If the method of recycling nutrients and using them to facilitate plant growth and improve plant health were developed and propagated, then we would be able to foster a more sustainable practice of agriculture and food consumption worldwide. This practice could help reduce the amount of greenhouse gas emissions produced by burning and processing organic waste such as food scraps and also reduce the harm to the environment regarding the use of chemical fertilizers, which would cause pollution and soil degradation.

4. Conclusion

In this experiment, I explored the method of composting. I found that the addition of coffee scrap in a ratio of 1:9 as a catalyst effectively boosted the performance of yard waste composting in terms of raising the composting pile core temperature. However, there might be an insuf-

efficient amount of composting materials in the composting pile such that the fermentation was ineffective and could not provide enough nutrients and structural support to aid plant growth. Nonetheless, these findings implied that composting could be a good choice for recycling organic waste generated from everyday life. I hope that further work on the minimum size of an effective composting pile can be done to outline a more specific method of composting that would help proliferate this practice around the world. I also hope that further work can be done on the effect of different organic fertilizers on the rate of composting, which could demonstrate the effectiveness of different kitchen waste as boosters, and eventually lead to a new way of kitchen waste reduction.

References

- [1] Robert Rynk and Et Al. *On-farm composting handbook : On farm composting handbook*. Ithaca, N.Y. Nraes, 1992. ISBN: 9780935817195.
- [2] USDA. *Food Waste FAQs*. URL: <https://www.usda.gov/foodwaste/faqs>.
- [3] James Bruggers. *Your Trash Is Emitting Methane In The Landfill. Here's Why It Matters For The Climate*. 2021. URL: <https://www.npr.org/2021/07/13/1012218119/epa-struggles-to-track-methane-from-landfills-heres-why-it-matters-for-the-clima>.
- [4] *8 methods of composting*. 2018. URL: https://directcompostsolutions.com/8-methods-composting/?srsltid=AfmBOoqcsmRHrLDb_pYdg2cAb9RxEi8hrRLa2LCQ3ijZk6Nh7LOiihRl.